

ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY AND SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF PARTICLE DISPERSED COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Aluminum(Al)-based metal matrix composites (MMCs) are expected to use as high-voltage transmission lines. Titanium diboride(TiB₂) particle is one of candidates as a reinforcing material because it exhibits high elastic modulus and hardness, high melting point and good thermal stability [1]. Moreover, the formation of brittle intermetallics at the reinforcement–matrix interface can be avoided because TiB₂ particles do not react with aluminum.

We have investigated the relation between mechanical properties and spatial distribution of reinforcing particles [2,3]. In the present work, we investigated the relationship between electrical conductivity and spatial distribution of TiB₂ particles using computer experiments.

2 Computer experiments

Finite volume method was used to calculate electrical potential distributions. Fig. 1 shows schematics of simulation model. Composite part is sandwiched by electrodes. The size of composite part was 100×100 meshes, and the size of electrodes was 5×100 meshes. The size of each mesh was 2×2 μm². Meshes of left-sided edge were set to 0.05V and other meshes were set to 0V as initial condition. Electrical conductivity of aluminum matrix, κ_{Al} , was set to 40.0[10⁶ · Ω⁻¹ · m⁻¹] and that of TiB₂ particle, κ_{TiB_2} , was set to 11.1[10⁶ · Ω⁻¹ · m⁻¹]. Electrical voltage was iteratively updated until average variation of electrical voltage of each mesh was lower than 10⁻¹³, and steady state of electrical potential distributions was obtained. Effective electrical conductivity of composite, κ_x , was evaluated with following equation,

$$\kappa_x = \frac{\kappa_{Al} V_{12} N_x}{V_{LR} - N_L V_{12} - N_R V_{12}} \quad (1)$$

where $N_x = 100$, $N_L = N_R = 5$ and $V_{LR} = 0.05$. V_{12} is average voltage difference between the first and the second column meshes in steady state. Effective electrical conductivity was evaluated with changing arrangement of TiB₂ particles and volume fraction. Five calculations with different seed of uniform and normal random number carried out in the same condition, and values are averaged.

Fig. 2 shows the distribution of 20vol.%TiB₂ particles in aluminum matrix. TiB₂ particles are arranged in (a) uniform random, (b)-(d) clustering, (e) parallel circuit and (f) series circuit arrangement. In order to make uniform random and clustering arrangement, TiB₂ particles were arranged with uniform and normal pseudorandom number, respectively. Clustering tendency was varied by changing the standard deviation, σ , of normal random number. When σ is small value, the particles arranges in clustering distribution. When σ is large value, distribution of particles approaches to uniform random distribution. The standard deviation, σ , of normal random number is referred as the clustering parameter hereafter.

Fig. 1 Schematics of simulation model.

Fig. 2. Distribution of 20vol.% TiB₂ particles in aluminum matrix. Color of TiB₂ particles and aluminum matrix are gray and black, respectively.

Fig. 3 shows the relationship between electrical conductivity and volume fraction. When TiB₂ particles are arranged in parallel, as shown in Fig. 2(e), electrical conductivity can be theoretically calculated by

$$\kappa_x = V_f \kappa_{TiB_2} + (1 - V_f) \kappa_{Al} \quad (2),$$

where V_f is volume fraction of TiB₂ particles. When TiB₂ particles are arranged in series, as shown in Fig. 2(f), electrical conductivity can be theoretically calculated by

$$\frac{1}{\kappa_x} = \frac{V_f}{\kappa_{TiB_2}} + \frac{1 - V_f}{\kappa_{Al}} \quad (3).$$

Solid and dashed lines in Fig. 3 represent these theoretical equations, and measured values (filled and open squares) which were obtained with

computer experiments agree with theoretical values in each volume fraction. This means that the evaluation method of effective electrical conductivity which was employed in this study is valid. Open circles in Fig. 3 represent effective electrical conductivities when TiB₂ particles are arranged in uniform random arrangement, as shown in Fig. 2(a), and plotted points are located between parallel and series theoretical lines. Filled circles in Fig. 3 represent effective electrical conductivities when TiB₂ particles are arranged in strong clustering arrangement, as shown in Fig. 2(d), and plotted points are located above points of uniform random arrangement. This means that effective electrical conductivities of clustering arrangement are higher than that of uniform random arrangement. Theoretical equation suggested by Chang et al. [4] are also plotted with a dotted line in Fig. 3, and measured effective electrical conductivities of uniform random and clustering arrangement in this study were lower than their model. In their model, particles are assumed to be arranged in an ordering configuration, and the difference of spatial distribution of particles possibly made a difference of effective electrical conductivities. These results suggest that spatial distribution of particles is an important parameter to consider electrical conductivity of particle dispersed composites.

In order to evaluate the spatial distribution of second

Fig. 3. The relationship between electrical conductivity and volume fraction.

phase particles quantitatively, 2-dimensional local number in random circle, LN2DR, were employed in this study. The definition of LN2DR are described below.

The number of gravity centers (GCs) of second phase particles in the measuring circle, whose center is put randomly, was defined as LN2DR. The radius of the measuring circle was determined so that the number density of the circle including GCs of 7 particles corresponds to the whole number density in 2-dimension, where 7 mean the number of a noticed particle and nearest neighbor particles in the measuring circle when assuming the closest hexagonal structure. The measuring radius, R_{2D} , is represented by

$$\frac{7}{\pi R_{2D}^2} = \lambda_A \Rightarrow R_{2D} = \left(\frac{7}{\pi \lambda_A} \right)^{1/2} = \frac{1.493}{\lambda_A^{1/2}}, \quad (4)$$

where λ_A is the whole number density. When GCs of second phase particles have the uniform random arrangement in 2-dimension, we can expected that the relative frequency distribution of LN2DR exhibits Poisson distribution and the probability of LN2DR is represented by

$$P(LN2D = k) = \frac{7^k}{k!} \exp(-7) \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (5)$$

The average and variance of this distribution are 7, respectively.

The measurement of LN2DR was carried out in two iterations. In the first, λ_A was calculated to count total number of GCs of second phase particles in images, and R_{2D} is determined by eq. (4). In the

Fig. 4 The measured relative frequency distribution of LN2DR for uniform random and clustering arrangement.

second, measuring circles with radius, R_{2D} , were put randomly in the images, and GCs included in each measuring circle were counted. One million samples were counted in one image, and relative frequency distributions were made.

Fig. 4 shows the relative frequency distribution which was measured from uniform random and clustering arrangement, Fig. 2(a)-(d). The relative frequency distribution of uniform random arrangement is the narrowest in the distributions, and that of clustering arrangement broaden with decreasing clustering parameter, σ . Since variance is the one of typical parameter which describes dispersion of relative frequency distributions, variance of LN2DR, $LN2DR_{var}$, was employed as a single scalar parameter to describe spatial distribution of second phase particles. When the spatial distribution of second phase particles approaches to uniform random arrangement, $LN2DR_{var}$ approaches to 7. When clustering tendency of second phase particles increases, $LN2DR_{var}$ increases. Fig. 5 shows the relationship between the clustering parameter and $LN2DR_{var}$. Spatial distribution of second phase particles is approximately represented with the parameter of $LN2DR_{var}$.

Fig. 6 shows the relationship between $LN2DR_{var}$ and effective electrical conductivities. In low volume fraction, such as 5%, electrical conductivities vary little with respect to $LN2DR_{var}$. In high volume fraction, such as 50%, electrical

Fig. 5 The relationship between the clustering parameter and variance of $LN2DR_{var}$.

Fig. 6 The relationship between LN2DR_{var} and electrical conductivities with respect to each volume fraction.

conductivities increase with increasing LN2DR_{var}. These results suggest that effective electrical conductivities increase in strong clustering arrangement of second phase particles and this tendency is enhanced in higher volume fraction. Furthermore, relationship between LN2DR_{var} and electrical conductivities is proportional in each volume fraction. Therefore, effective electrical conductivity, κ_x , can be approximated by following equation,

$$\kappa_x = ax + b \quad (6),$$

where x is LN2DR_{var}. Slope, a , and intercept, b , for each volume fraction were calculated by least-square method, and the best fitted lines are plotted in Fig. 6.

Fig. 7 shows relation of volume fraction to slope, a , and intercept, b . Filled circles represent best fitted a and b . Moreover, a and b can be approximated by following equations,

$$a = pV_f^2 \quad (7),$$

$$b = qV_f^2 + (\kappa_{TiB_2} - \kappa_{Al} - q)V_f + \kappa_{Al} \quad (8),$$

where p and q is fitting parameter. Parameters, p and q , was calculated by least-square method, and the best fitted lines are plotted in Fig. 7, where $p = 0.2624$ and $q = 26.479$. Summarizing equations (6) to (8), following experimental equation including a parameter of spatial distribution of second phase particles, LN2DR_{var}, is derived.

$$\kappa_x = (px + q)V_f^2 + (\kappa_{TiB_2} - \kappa_{Al} - q)V_f + \kappa_{Al} \quad (9).$$

Fig. 7 Relation of volume fraction to slope, a , and intercept, b .

Fig. 8 shows ordering distribution of TiB₂ particles. TiB₂ particles are arranged (a) in vertical direction, (b) in horizontal direction, (c) with space and (d) in cross-shaped. Electrical conductivity and LN2DR_{var} were evaluated in these ordering arrangements. Table 1 shows a comparison between measured electrical conductivities and predicted electrical conductivities by equation (9). As far as second phase particles are arranged in uniform random or clustering configuration, equation (9) can predict electrical conductivities accurately. However, when second phase particles arranged in ordering configuration, equation (9) cannot predict electrical conductivities accurately. In the measurement of LN2DR, orientation anisotropy of second phase particles is not considered, and therefore, equation (9) is not enough to analyze composites with directionally oriented particle arrangement.

Fig. 8 Ordering distribution of TiB₂ particles. Color of TiB₂ particles and aluminum matrix are gray and black, respectively.

Table 1. Comparison between measured electrical conductivities, κ_x , and predicted electrical conductivities by equation (9). Unit of κ_x is $10^6 \cdot \Omega^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$.

	V_f	LN2D R_{var}	Eq. (9) κ_x	Measured κ_x
Uniform	0.25	5.59	27.9	27.8
Clustering ($\sigma=0.3$)	0.25	13.5	28.0	27.9
Clustering ($\sigma=0.1$)	0.25	110	29.6	29.4
Vertical	0.5	0.814	19.0	17.3
Horizontal	0.5	0.532	19.0	25.4
Space	0.25	0.737	27.8	28.6
Cross	0.5	0.742	19.0	17.3

3 Electrical conductivity of Al-20vol.%TiB₂ composites

Al-20vol.%TiB₂ particle-dispersed composites were prepared with powder metallurgical processes. Mean size of Al powder (99.9% purity) was 3 μm and that of TiB₂ powder (99.9% purity) was 2.62 μm . Two types of powder blending method, wet blending in ethanol and dry blending were used. Blending was performed with ball milling machine for 16h.

Samples were consolidated by spark plasma sintering (SPS). Details of the material preparation will be presented elsewhere. Fig. 9 (a) and (b) show the typical microstructures of wet-blending sample and dry-blending sample, respectively. TiB₂ particles in dry-blending sample arranges in clustering arrangement as compared with wet-blending sample. Electrical conductivities of samples were measured with four-terminal method. The electrical conductivity of wet-blending sample was $22[10^6 \cdot \Omega^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}]$ and that of dry-blending sample was $27[10^6 \cdot \Omega^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}]$. These experimental results suggest that the electrical conductivity of a sample with stronger clustering distribution of TiB₂ particles tends to increase. This tendency corresponds to that obtained from computer experiments. Spatial distribution of TiB₂ particles in Fig. 9 was evaluated with LN2DR_{var}. Table 2 shows measured LN2DR_{var}, predicted κ_x by equation (9) and measured κ_x . The measured κ_x is lower than the predicted κ_x .

Fig. 9 Microstructure of Al-20vol.%TiB₂ particle-dispersed composites. (a) wet-blending sample, (b) dry-blending sample.

Table 2. Measured electrical conductivity, κ_x , and spatial distribution of Al-20vol.%TiB₂ particle-dispersed composites. Comparison with electrical conductivity predicted by equation (9) is shown. Unit of κ_x is $10^6 \cdot \Omega^{-1} \cdot m^{-1}$.

	V_f	LN2D R_{var}	Eq. (9) κ_x	Measured κ_x
Wet-blending	0.2	8.05	30.0	22
Dry-blending	0.2	13.88	30.1	27

It seems that residual stress affect to the degradation of electrical conductivity. The residual stress occurs in a matrix in a cooling process of the composites preparation. The residual stress generates the lattice distortion, and degrades the electrical conductivity.

4 Conclusion

We investigated the relationship between electrical conductivity and spatial distribution of TiB₂ particles using computer experiments. Spatial distribution of the particles was evaluated with variance of 2-dimensional local number in random circle, LN2DR_{var}. Following conclusions are derived from the current study.

- (1) Making a comparison in uniform random arrangement, electrical conductivity decreased with increasing volume fraction of TiB₂ particles.
- (2) Making comparison in clustering arrangement, electrical conductivity increased with increasing degree of clustering tendency of TiB₂ particles.
- (3) Electrical conductivity of uniform random and clustering arrangement can be expressed by experimental equation (9). However, this equation was not enough to analyze ordering arrangement of TiB₂ particles.

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